

Women Entrepreneur's Constraints

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Introduction

Entrepreneurship is known to be as a male-dominated word from a very early age, but time has changed the situation and brought women as today's most memorable and inspirational entrepreneurs. It is estimated that women entrepreneurs currently comprise about ten percent of the total number of entrepreneurs in India, with the percentage growing every year. If the prevailing trends continue, it is likely that in another five years, women will comprise twenty percent of the entrepreneurial force.

Women form a vital part of the labour force and the economic role played by them cannot be isolated from the framework of development. The part and notch of integration of women in the development of the economy is always an indicator of women's independence and to give her social status. Employment gives economic independence to women. Economic independence paves the way for social status. Moreover, women have become an integral part of industrialized society. Women's entry into entrepreneurship has a historical perspective and it is a historical necessity. Entrepreneurship has become an active tool for social and economic development. It helps in generating employment for many people within their social system. The development of entrepreneurship in women especially in developing economies like India is viewed as the most effective package to solve the blockades to the prosperity of the nation although it envisages revision and re-examination of long-standing attitudes, expectations and patterns of living.

The World Bank states that the empowerment of women is fundamental in achieving continued sustainable development and that succeeding in this effort could enhance economic efficiency. Because business and entrepreneurship are still perceived in many countries and cultures as a male-dominated sphere, it remains a priority to provide women with equal access to opportunities and constant research on female entrepreneurship could assist in doing so.

Women Entrepreneurs

Women entrepreneur is known as an individual who takes a thought-provoking role to meet her requirements and become

economically self-determining. A tough aspiration to do something positive is an inbuilt quality of entrepreneurial women, who are capable of contributing ethics in both family and social life. The drives for being entrepreneurship have also established systematic attention, with various authors referring to gender inequality as a push factor for female entrepreneurship in developed and developing economies.

Several women entrepreneurs have the excellent of self-employment that replicates the restricted structure of prospects in the labour market, labour market discrimination or glass ceiling career problems, with self-employment often observed as an existence approach, or as a means of providing flexibility in work scheduling and reconciling multiple roles. Many factors attracting the entrepreneurship are also expressively revolving around chances for freedom, task, initiative as well as the success and satisfaction derived through entrepreneurship, with research suggesting different employment opportunities for men and women entrepreneurs, revolving around status attainment for the former and social relationships and goals for the latter.

The Government of India defines, “An enterprise owned and controlled by women having a minimum financial interest of 51% of capital and giving at least 51% of the employment generated by the enterprise to women”. Thus it is marked that the definition of an entrepreneur can be generalised to women entrepreneur too.

The challenges and opportunities for women entrepreneurs are growing rapidly. In our country, even though women constitute the majority of the total population, the entrepreneurial still seem like a male-dominated one, which makes women entrepreneurs to often face some major problems in running their enterprise successfully. Many women entrepreneurs are either housewives or illiterates or a fresh graduate with no previous experience of running a business enterprise.

Why Women as Entrepreneurs?

Human resources comprise of men and women, of different working-age, constitute the main strength of economic development of a nation. Their share is an important segment of the total labour force and the economic role played by them cannot be isolated from the framework of development. Women’s role and degree of integration in an economic expansion is always an indicator of women’s economic independence and social status. Employment gives economic independence to women. Economic independence paves the way for social status. Moreover, women have become an integral part of industrialized society. A woman must supplement the income of the family through whatever skill she possesses or has acquired. The present inflationary pressures warrant women to join the male members of the family for securing a substantial livelihood.

It seems to be perfect for women who are seeking participation in the country’s economic development due to certain factors. The rise of entrepreneurship is considered to be closely linked to social, cultural, religious and psychological variables.

Review of Literature

Karim in his study on women entrepreneurs in Bangladesh have found that financial difficulties were the most common problems faced by many women entrepreneurs, particularly in rural areas and he also pointed that Competition, procurement of quality raw materials, and balancing time between the enterprise and the family were ranked as major start-up problems.

Hookimsing and Essoin in their study have recognized four main hurdles faced by women entrepreneurs such as the hassle of getting permits, the lack of market, the ability to raise the investment needed and the like.

A study conducted by Soyeon Shim and Eastlick identify ten business problem areas such as sales and profit forecasting; obtaining lines of credit; capital management; working capital management;

pricing policies; customers information; short-term business planning; labour cost analysis; managing debt; and gender problems. Many researchers feel that tension between personal lives and career pursuits is the most significant problem that women entrepreneurs face.

Jamali examines various constraints and opportunities affecting women entrepreneurship and clearly illustrates the relevance of micro- and macro-level factors in entrepreneurship to manage the complexity of the women entrepreneurship in any particular context.

Sarbapriya and Ishitain their study, while discussing the status and problems faced by women entrepreneurs, emphasized on significant differences between women entrepreneurs and the men entrepreneurs on the ground of perseverance, potentiality and ability to work hard, as well as the abilities specific to emotional intelligence.

Constraints Faced by Women

Women in India have faced many problems to get ahead of their life in business. Women entrepreneurs face a series of problems right from the beginning to the enterprise functions. The difficulties of women in India are a concern with her responsibility towards family, society and work.

The problems that the Indian women are coming across while they enter into entrepreneurship such as traditions, customs, socio-cultural values, ethics, motherhood, physically weak, feelings of insecurity and the like. It is also found that women in rural areas have to suffer more than women in the urban. They face tough resistance from men. They are considered as helpers. The view of the society towards women and problems in which they have to live and work are not very beneficial.

In addition to the above basic problems the other problems faced by women entrepreneurs are as follows:

1. Family Ties

Women in India are very sensitively attached to their families. Women have to do all the domestic work in the home, to take care of the children and other members of the family. Women have an extra burden with family tasks like taking care of husband, children and in-laws, which take away a lot of their time and energy. In such a situation, it will be very difficult to concentrate and run the enterprise successfully.

2. Male-Dominated Society

At present even though we and our constitution speak about the equality between sexes, male prejudice is still the order of the day. It is to be noted that women are not treated equally to men. Women's entry to business requires the approval of the head of the family. Traditionally, entrepreneurship has been seen as a male preserve. This domination comes to end in the growth of women entrepreneurs.

3. Lack of Education

In India, Women are falling behind in the field of education. Many women in rural areas are illiterate. One who is literate is provided either less or inadequate education than the male due to early marriage, sometimes due to their son's higher education and the remaining due to poverty. Due to inappropriate education women, entrepreneurs are in lack of knowledge about the development of new technology, new methods of production, marketing and other governmental support which will encourage them to flourish.

4. Social Barriers

The customs and traditions prevailed in Indian societies towards women now and then stand as a hindrance before them to grow and prosper. Another hindrance of women entrepreneurs is castes and religions dominate with one another. More than the urban area women face more social barriers in rural areas.

5. Shortage of Raw Materials

The shortage of raw materials and the accessibility of proper adequate raw materials sound the death-knell of the enterprises run by women entrepreneurs. Women entrepreneurs face difficulties in getting the essential raw material and other required inputs for their enterprises when the prices are very high.

6. Problem of Finance

Women entrepreneurs have to overcome a lot in raising and meeting the financial needs of the business. Bankers, creditors and financial institutes are not coming forward to provide financial assistance to women borrowers on the ground of their less creditworthiness and more chances of business failure. Women face more financial problem due to the shortage of funds for the purchase of raw materials, work-in-progress finished goods and non-receipt of payment from customers in time.

7. Tough Competition

Generally, women entrepreneurs adopt outdated technology in the process of production. In the market where the competition is too high, women entrepreneurs have to fight hard to endure in the market against the organized sector and their male counterpart who has enormous experience and capacity to adopt advanced technology in managing enterprises.

8. The High Cost of Production

Several factors including disorganized management incur the high cost of production, which acts as a stumbling block before women entrepreneurs. Women entrepreneurs face technology obsolescence due to non-adoption or slow adoption to changing technology, which is a major factor of the high cost of production.

9. Low Risk-Bearing Capacity

In India, women by nature are weak, shy and mild. Women cannot bear the amount risk which is essential for running an enterprise. The other factors like improper education, training and financial support from outsiders also reduce their ability to bear the risk involved in an enterprise.

10. Limited Mobility

Women flexibility in India is very inadequate and has become problematic due to traditional values and inability to drive vehicles. Moving along and asking for a room to stay out in the night for business purposes are still looked upon with suspicious eyes. Now and then, younger women feel uncomfortable in dealing with men who show extra interest in them than work-related aspects.

11. Lack of Entrepreneurial Aptitude

Lack of entrepreneurial aptitude is a matter of concern for women entrepreneurs. They have no entrepreneurial bent of mind. Even after attending various training programmes on entrepreneurship women entrepreneurs fail to tide over the risks and troubles that may come up in an organizational working.

12. Limited Managerial Ability

The process of management has become a specified work which only efficient managers can perform. But it is found that women entrepreneurs are not efficient in managerial functions like planning, organizing, controlling, coordinating, staffing, directing, motivating etc. of an enterprise. Therefore, the less and limited managerial ability of women has become a problem for them to run the enterprise successfully.

13. Legal Formalities

Satisfying the legal formalities obligatory for running an enterprise is a disturbance assignment on the part of a women entrepreneur because of the dominance of unethical practices in government offices and bureaucratic delays for various licenses, electricity, water and shed allotments. In such circumstances, women entrepreneurs find it hard to focus on the smooth working of the enterprise.

14. Exploitation by Middlemen

Women solely not able to perform the functions like marketing, distribution and money collection so that they have to depend on middlemen for the above activities. Middlemen try to cheat them in the semblance of helping. They add their profit margin, which results in fewer sales and lesser profit.

15. Lack of Self-confidence

Women due to their inherent nature, lack self-confidence, which is essentially a motivating factor in running an enterprise successfully, have to struggle hard to make a balance between managing a family and managing an enterprise. Occasionally she has to sacrifice her entrepreneurial urge to strike a balance between the two.

Supportive Measures for Women Entrepreneurs

Women Entrepreneurs can be seen everywhere in the startup-up ecosystem in India. It has been noticed that women are leaving their high-profile jobs as well as some stepping out of the four walls of their homes and joining the pool of Entrepreneurship in India.

The Indian Government has adopted the principle of Women's equality in all spheres of life. Since Independence, several steps have been taken by the government for the progress of women through successive Five Year Plans. The Sixth Five Year Plan draft for the first time incorporated a new chapter entitled 'Women and Development' with special stress on the issue of the development of women entrepreneurship. To support women entrepreneurship, multidimensional efforts have been formulated in India, which are enumerated below:

1. Direct and Indirect financial support
2. Yojna, schemes and program
3. Technological training and Awards
4. Federations and Associations
 - National Alliance of you of Entrepreneurs (NAYE)
 - Indian Council of Women Entrepreneurs (ICWE)
 - Self-employed Women's Association (SEWA)/
 - Association of Women Entrepreneurs of Karnataka (AWEK)
5. Annapurna Scheme
6. Stree Shakti Package for Women entrepreneurs
7. Cent Kalyani scheme
8. Mudra Yojana scheme
9. MahilaUdyamNidhi scheme
10. Dena Shakti scheme
11. Orient MahilaVikasYojana scheme
12. BhartiyaMahila Bank Business loan

Conclusion

At present entrepreneurs are desired to society to increase the economic value of the country and to provide a career for the young peoples. Entrepreneurs should be positive and open-minded and he or she must have enough knowledge about the business. The market conditions and technology should be updated regularly and this may help them to be successful in the business.

Entrepreneurs face various constraints while running an enterprise. For every problem there are solutions but it does not mean that entrepreneurs will never face any problem since they know the solutions for every problem. Finance is the major problem faced by many of the entrepreneurs while starting their entrepreneurial venture. By personal savings, getting debt from the bank and

by getting government subsidies this problem can be rectified. They must have enough strength to face the challenge and get success in their business. The main strength of the entrepreneurs is self-confidence and weakness is fear of failure which they have while starting their business. Thus, they have confidence in her capacity to deal with the world and take practical steps to attain the goals.

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